

Planning and modelling of Pharmaceuticals Wholesale-Distributors supply Chain using SCOR model: A Moroccan case study

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Abstract

The evolution of the economic, social and regulatory environment in addition to the specificity of pharmaceutical products requires the pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors, in order to maintain and improve their performance, to be more competitive, agile and responsive to different constraints and criteria imposed by the various players in the supply chain and by the environmental uncertainty. The development of models that integrate the sharing information amongst supply partners, at all decision levels with uncertainty consideration is a key success factor to achieve these objectives and to increase organizational productivity and profitability.

This paper presents an adaptation of the SCOR processes to the pharmaceuticals Wholesale-Distributors supply chain. The purpose is twofold:

- *The SCOR model is widely acknowledged as the quasi-industry standard for SCM. However, its application within Moroccan enterprises still postponed. This article has as main interest to fill this gap.*
- *SCOR modelling is the first step in our approach which aims at setting up a dynamic and efficient decision-making system in supply chain management of pharmaceuticals wholesale distributors and that consider the uncertainty. SCOR model assists to better map and analyses the entire supply chain. Moreover, it provides key performance indicators that we will also adapt and use in our system.*

Future works will be devoted to the same dual objective: (i) adapting and enriching SCOR performance indicators to suit pharmaceuticals distribution and (ii) the fulfillment of the decision-making system.

Keywords: Supply chain management, Pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors, SCOR, Model adaptation.

I. Introduction

The evolution of enterprises and market conditions has made the supply chain management receiving a particular interest from both academics and practitioners (Parrod & Thierry, 2007) leading to the development of new tools and approaches whose adoption helps companies to improve, implement and manage their supply chains. Among these tools, we can find general models and others more specific (Ducq, Wadwah, & Vallespir, n.d.). the SCOR model of the APICS- SCC is the world's most recognized supply chain model and widely acknowledged as the quasi-industry standard for SCM. It is used by companies from both industrial and services sectors. However, the adoption of SCOR still postponed in Morocco and other developing countries. This lateness can be explained by the fact that the model has been developed and tested on the basis of the experiences of companies from developed countries (Georgise et al., 2016). The same idea of (Garcia & Giachetti, 2010) who mentioned that SCOR reflects the practices of more developed countries. The nature of developing countries companies (Morocco as an example), their conditions (infrastructure, ICT) and business processes vary considerably from those of developed countries. Furthermore, Different researchers worked on SCOR and stated that the model is too general and requires efforts of adaptation to local operating conditions.

On a Moroccan level, we have noticed a rareness of studies and gaps (Essajide & Rachidi, 2016) on the SCOR model utilization. Only two studies deals with this subject; (Radouane Lemghari, Driss Sarsri, 2015) who used it to assess the automotive supply chain and (Imane Ibn El Farouk, Abdennebi Talbi, 2012) who applied the SCOR to evaluate the performance of logistic activities in Moroccan hospitals.

The present article joins these few researchers and focuses on adapting SCOR processes to pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors supply chain. It provides a new perspective for these enterprises operating as intermediaries between laboratories and pharmacies and ensures the availability of medicines throughout the Moroccan territory. They guarantee to citizens the access to medicines (whether geographical access: medicine available to everyone wherever he is or physical access: medicines accessible at all times) with quality and safety. Nonetheless, the wholesale distributors face several difficulties and constraints in

the internal and external environment causing a sharp deterioration of both profitability and operational performance.

This article aims three main objectives: firstly, to highlight the different difficulties that Moroccan pharmaceuticals wholesale distributors face. Secondly to present and understand their supply chain and finally to propose a business process for an adapted SCOR model, which can be used to map, assess and improve their supply chain. (except the Enable process that will be discussed in a further work).

The paper is structured as follow: the second section presents the Moroccan pharmaceuticals distribution sector, its organization, and challenges. In the third section, we will describe the SCOR model, the reason for choosing SCOR and a review of its adaptation to different contexts. the research methodology, the modelling of pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors supply chain using SCOR 11.0 and the proposed SCOR changes are discussed in the fourth section. The last section is devoted to the discussion of different results, limitations, and perspectives of the research.

II. Overview of Moroccan pharmaceuticals distribution

1. Pharmaceuticals Value chain

Pharmaceutical industry occupies a very important socio-economic place due to the particularity of pharmaceutical products. This particularity is justified by several reasons (Amri, 2016) :

- Pharmaceuticals are intended for consumers who are in special circumstances, and any unavailability or failure could involve his life.
- Pharmaceuticals are products that their consumption directly affects the human body. Therefore, any possible error in its manufacture or distribution (use of the expired drug, erroneous prescription of a drug,) would have very serious consequences on the health of the patient.

The pharmaceutical value chain (figure 1) involves three major components(IMS institute for healthcare Informatics, 2014) :

- Manufacturing of the medicine: it starts with research and development and finally by gaining regulatory approval which allows a medicine to be sold in a market.
- Distribution of the dispensing points: it includes transportation and distribution of medicines to the wholesale-distributors, community pharmacies hospital pharmacies, clinics
- Dispensing to the end user.

Figure 1: Pharmaceutical value Chain ((Taylor, Monique, & Elias, 2004)

Medicines distribution is the link between manufacturers and patients in the pharmaceutical “value chain” ((Taylor et al., 2004). In Morocco, the two primary distribution actors are wholesale-distributors and community pharmacies; They distribute more than 79%¹ (figure 2).

Generally, we distinguish two distribution circuits (details in section IV):

- Direct circuit: linking laboratories directly to pharmacies, clinics, hospitals
- Indirect circuit: Wholesale-distributors supply pharmacies, hospitals.

figure 2: Pharmaceuticals distribution channels (Moroccan Pharmaceutical Industry Association & IMS health)

2. Moroccan pharmaceuticals Wholesale-distributors

The Moroccan wholesale-distributors ensure the availability and the continuous supply of medicines in 11.000² community pharmacies throughout the Moroccan territory. Prior to 1977³, there were only 4 wholesale distributors, and 95% of the total stock of medicines was concentrated in Casablanca- Rabat. This number grew exponentially and reached 12 wholesale distributors in 1987, 36 in 2002 and 65 in 2012. Currently, the number has decreased to 58. In terms of coverage, there are groups covering almost all of Moroccan territory, and others with broad coverage of most regions by deliveries up to 5 times a day. Community pharmacies supply is guaranteed even on weekends and on public holidays. In spite of this, Wholesale-distributors encounter several difficulties and constraints (figure 3):

- Internal environment Constraints (between supply chain actors):
 - Lack of coordination between supply chain actors,
 - A large number of community pharmacies have financial difficulties. This situation has repercussions on wholesale-distributors by increasing the number of unpaid invoices and litigations. According to (Conseil de la Concurrence du Maroc, 2014), there are more than 3000 pharmacies risking bankruptcy and who were banned from check books facilities.
- Constraints related to the market structure :
 - Community pharmacies are dispersed (atomization of pharmacies and concentration of laboratories). This situation raises the wholesale-distributors charges which are mainly related to vehicle fleet and fuel and subsequently it decreases their net margin. This net margin is 10% of the Moroccan medicine public price (PPM). Given that medicines have a unified price anywhere in Morocco, wholesalers cannot in any case compensate transport costs by the price of medicines;
 - The low domestic consumption: the annual expenditure on the purchase of medicines in Morocco are considered very low compared to other countries. These expenses are estimated

¹ Moroccan Pharmaceutical Industry Association & IMS health.

² Lahcen Senhaji, “Distribution Pharmaceutique : Secteur Incontournable dans l’accès aux médicaments : Etat des lieux et propositions de solutions”.

³ Moroccan ministry of health: Politique pharmaceutique nationale, rapport 2013

at 415Dhs per person (2015 statistics)⁴, i.e., 42.67 \$ against 596 \$ in France, 1026 \$ in the USA);

- The narrowness of domestic market
- Legislative pressures:
 - Drug prices decrease subsequently distributors margins decrease;
 - The liberalization of petroleum products: this element in addition to telephone costs constitute the two major items in the act of distribution (Senhaji, 2013);
 - According to Law 009-741, Wholesale-distributors must hold a security stock equal to 1/12 of their total sales of the previous year. The security stock must be consisting of at least 80% of all the medicines approved in Morocco.

Figure 3: Moroccan Pharmaceuticals supply chain challenges and difficulties

The wholesale-distributors supply chain became increasingly complex. In addition to the previous difficulties, the uncertainties and risks are important factors which may distort the supply chain management.

III. Overview of the SCOR model

Supply Chain modelling and assessment has long been perceived as one of the competitiveness strategies in scientific research (Bete, Corresponding, & Seifert, 2012). Several reviews on SCM (Eleaz & El-baz, 2015) (Estampe, Lamouri, Paris, & Brahim-djelloul, 2013) (Estampe, 2013) (Georgise et al., 2016) (Balfaqih, Saibani, & Al-nory, 2016) have shown that most of the researches in Supply Chain Management in recent years had focused on supply chain model and performance assessment. The most well-known models are: (i) SCOR of the APICS-SCC, Ohio University's Global Supply Chain Forum (GSCF) framework, ASLOG, Global EVALOG, American Productivity & Quality's PCF (Process Classification Framework) Center. Among these models, we chose to work on the SCOR model for numerous reasons:

- SCOR can be considered as a supply chain modelling standard. It is the most well-known and mature model in this field. SCOR has been revised and enriched several times. All supply chain processes and activities are well represented in it. By SCOR modelling we will have a complete and global picture of the wholesale-distributors supply chain.
- SCOR provides performance indicators for all levels of the company (from strategic to operational) and for all processes. The hierarchical nature of these indicators makes it possible to diagnose the supply chain, which subsequently facilitates root cause analyzes.

⁴ OECD health statistics 2015

- SCOR facilitates the understanding of the company's decision-making system.

1. SCOR model

The SCOR model is a top down approach to supply chain assessment with a holistic business view of the entire supply chain and its processes (Husby & Swartwood, 2012). It combines elements of business process engineering, benchmarking and best practices in a single framework. SCOR is organized around the six primary management processes (figure 4) of Plan, Source, Make, Deliver, Return and Enable (Supply Chain Council, 2012) from the suppliers' supplier to the customers' customer, and all aligned with a company's operational strategy, material, work, and information flow (Bolstorff & Rosenbaum, 2003).

Figure 4: SCOR model (Supply Chain council)

The "Enable" Process became a level one process in the revision 11.0. This allowed the model to be closed loop, similar to ISO 9000 models.

the model is designed to support supply chain analysis at multiple levels. SCC has focused on the top three process levels, which are industry neutral. Repair and overhaul product."

- Level 1: define scope and content of a supply chain. At level 1 the basis of competition performance targets for a supply chain is set.
- Level 2: define the operations strategy. At level 2 the process capabilities for a supply chain are set.
- Level 3: define the configuration of individual processes. At level 3 the ability to execute is set. The focus of this level is on the right processes, inputs and outputs, process performance, practices, technology capabilities and skills of staff.

Beyond level 3 is not included in the reference model. Every organization that implements supply chain improvements using the SCOR model will need to extend the model, at least to Level-4, using industry-, organization- and/or location-specific processes, systems, and practices. Improving the performance of supply chain processes and performance indicators optimization remain the main objectives of SCOR (Paul & Laville, 2007).

2. Analyse of related researches of the SCOR model

The objective of this section is to demonstrate the applicability of the SCOR model to all sectors and to different operating conditions. We do not attempt in any case to present and identify every study on SCOR.

Before presenting these researches, it will be interesting to evocate its different revisions (table 1). A SCOR revision is normally implemented when SCC members believe that changes are needed to promote the continuous effective use of the model. The first version of SCOR dates back to the year 1996; Then the model has had 13 revisions. The latest revision is the year 2012 with the SCOR 11.0.

Year	SCOR revision	Changes
1996	1.0	The first version of the model : Plan, Source, Make, Deliver, performance indicators
1998	2.0	changes in the model to show distinctions between discrete and process industries
1999	3.0	Model modified to enhance infrastructure elements; specific reference to software products removed; input and output enhanced
2000	3.1	Definition of metrics attributes. Language to support services as well as tangible goods.
2001	4.0 5.0	- Return processes introduced, E-business practiced updated ,metrics restructuring continued.
2003	6.0	3 changes in ‘‘retail’’ processes. ‘‘Deliver retail product’’ added. Reconfiguration of ‘‘R2:return of maintenance,, Best practices added to the concept of Electronic business.
2004	6.1	Restructuration of Return processes and metrics added to measure these processes. Add and review of best practices in ‘‘collaborative planning forecasting and replenishment, sales, and operations planning, supplier’s assessment and supplier carrier agreements.
2005	7.0	Restructuration and simplification of the performance indicators: first level metrics reduced from 13 to 9. Processes of the third level were extended. Appendix of a detailed description of the first level metrics was attached to the model.8 new best practices were added, and explained.
2006	8.0	A number of revisions in : performance indicators (new one added ‘‘ Return on working capital’’) others have been simplified, best practices appendix reworked, and workflow diagrams and the SCOR database.
2008	9.0	The major's additions ‘‘ risk management and green capabilities’’ and metrics are updated.
2010	10.0	‘‘People’’ is added to the model. It outlined training needs and individual performance measures for each of the core process elements.
2012	11.0	Latest version. Some metrics’’costs’’ changed by others. And other metric removed; ‘‘Enable’’ process became a level 1 process; best practices are categorized and linked to processes and performance indicators.

Table 1: SCOR model revisions (adapted from SCC publications)

Several researchers and practitioners have been working on adapting the SCOR model to their local operational conditions. Indeed companies operate in different industries with conditions and challenges specific to them. It is necessary to find and adapt SCM approaches and models to the business processes and environmental conditions of each company.(Shewchuk, 1998) said ‘‘

Although SCOR was originally developed to improve the processes of manufacturing enterprises (Poluha, 2007), its use is not limited to. The model has been used in the services sector as well (Barnard, 2006). As examples, (Mihalis, 2011) worked on the utility of the SCOR in services and developed a

reference model for use in service organisations. In his research, services are considered as supply chain processes that are balanced around the capacity of the firm through the upstream sourcing processes. The developed model conceptualises the capacity of service firms as a resource inventory to build a service offering. This inventory-capacity duality that describes a service firm's capabilities is applicable across a wide spectrum of the service sector. Six major processes for the design and management of service supply chains are identified: plan, source, develop, adapt, operate, and recover. (Baltacioglu, Ada, Kaplan, Yurt, & Kaplan, 2007) proposed a general supply chain model "IUE-SCC" for the services industry derived from SCOR and Ellram's et al. models (Ellram, Tate, & Billington, 2004). The model includes all elements of the supply chain and defines the managerial activities to be fulfilled for effective management of service supply chains. They also implemented the model for the healthcare industry. Researchers as (Gerosa & Taisch, n.d.) (Barnard, 2006) (Baltacioglu et al., 2007) and others also worked with SCOR either by adapting it to services sector or by using it as a basis for the development of frameworks for services supply chains.

beyond services sector, SCOR has been used in many industrial sectors (transport, textile, electrical manufacturing, and recycling, shipbuilding...).

(Schnetzler, Lemm, Bonfils, & Thees, 2009) applied the model to the Swiss forest sector; they transposed the SCOR processes to wood supply, harvesting, delivery and forest planning. Similarly, (Moreira, Westlund, & Lebel, 2011) developed, using the SCOR model, a framework for describing any wood supply chain. (Svensson & Hvolby, 2012) have established using SCOR a business process model for universities. SCOR is also applied to tourism. (Yilmaz, 2006) demonstrated the utility of SCOR in measuring and managing tourism value chain processes. (Wibowo & Nur, 2015)(Cheng, Law, Bjornsson, Jones, & Sriram, 2010) applied the model for performance assessment and analysis in the constructions field. The first ones combined SCOR indicator and AHP method (Analytical Hierarchy Process), while (Cheng et al., 2010) presented a service-oriented architecture based on the SCOR model for the control constructions supply chains.

(Bete et al., 2012) analyzed 28 papers and theses on SCOR applications. They classified those applications into 5 categories according to the SCOR application environment:

- Manufacturing industry environment;
- Services environment;
- Military environment;
- Geographical information system (GIS) and information technology (IT) environment;
- Logistics operation's environment;
- Collaborative supply network environment.

From the researches presented, we can conclude that the SCOR model can be adapted to different environments and contexts even far from the scope of SCOR. Researchers and practitioners agree on the contribution of the model to improving the performance of the logistics chain.

In the following, we will present the research methodology, and the SCOR modelling of the pharmaceuticals Wholesale-distributors supply chains.

IV. SCOR modelling and planning of Pharmaceuticals Wholesale-Distributors supply chain : Case of Morocco

The results below are the first step of our research that aims to setting up a dynamic and efficient decision-making system in supply chain management of pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors and that consider the uncertainties (ESSAJIDE & Rachidi, 2017) that may affect the proper management of the supply chain and subsequently the availability of medicines and the profitability of the wholesale-distributors.

Our approach is based initially on the descriptive and detailed modelling of the pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors. The purpose behind choosing the SCOR model is twofold:

- Among the various supply chain models and tools that we have studied, the SCOR model is the most mature one, and that is considered as a standard in SCM. Its hierarchical approach gives a holistic

business view of the entire supply chain and its processes. This will allow a better understanding of the pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributor supply chain and its decision-making system. In addition, SCOR provides a set of performance indicators.

- We noticed that despite the worldwide recognition of the SCOR model, its use still postponed in Morocco. The essential causes of this delay are identified above. This paper has as primary interest to fill this gap and to present a new perspective to Moroccan enterprises in general and especially to commercial ones.

1. Methodology

The analysis of different researches on the modelling and assessment of the supply chains reveals two predominant approaches: the case study and the conceptual approach. We adopted the case study. It's the proper approach to adapt and to verify the suitability of the model.

We worked on a pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributor located in Agadir, South of Morocco. It operates throughout the Moroccan territory, capitalizes an important expertise and collaborates with more than 1000 customers and 600 suppliers. It also has two subsidiaries.

We have been involved in the different activities (sourcing, transporting, customer's order preparation, delivering). We also relied on the procedures manuals of the enterprise and the supply chain operation references revision 11.0.

2. Results

This section recaps the field results. To understand the whole supply chain, the first sub-section will present the two firsts SCOR levels where the entire supply chain actors are introduced. The research focus 'wholesale-distributors' and the adapted SCOR processes (except the Enable process that will be studied in a further work) will be specified in the second sub-section. A global view of the supply chain of the source stocked product will be presented in the 3rd sub-section.

2.1. SCOR Level 1 & level 2 modelling

The pharmaceuticals distribution supply chain consists of 4 tiers (figure 5):

- Tier 1: Laboratories: suppliers and producers of pharmaceuticals
- Tier 2: Distribution Companies: Wholesale-distributors
- Tier 3: Community pharmacies, Public hospitals, military hospitals, clinics, prisons, University hospital
- Tier 4: Patients and pharmaceuticals users.

Figure 5: SCOR level 1 modelling

Laboratories in Morocco market:

- Medicines made by themselves.

- Medicines whose manufacture is outsourced to other laboratories-partners ((Chrifi, Echchtabi, & Charkaoui, 2015)
- Medicines imported under licenses from foreign laboratories.

Laboratories supplies both domestic and export market. The Moroccan Pharmaceutical production covers 65% of national needs and exports up to 8% of the total production.

figure 6: SCOR level 2 modelling

Figure 6 illustrate SCOR level 2 and the focus of the study. The notation respects that of the SCOR reference model. The letter ‘s’ refers to SCOR, the second letter refers to the process: S ‘Source’, P ‘Plan’, M ‘Make’, D ‘Deliver’, SR ‘Source Return’ and DR for ‘Deliver Return’.

4 different channels to distinguish (2 distribution circuits (direct & indirect⁵) and 4 channels):

- Laboratories → Wholesale-Distributors → Community pharmacies/ hospitals / clinics / university hospital/ prisons → users
- Laboratories → Hospital university/Clinics → users
- Laboratories → community pharmacies → users
- Laboratories → department of procurement → hospitals / prisons ... → users: the procurements department plays the role of a central purchasing office. It launches a call for tender and distributes the pharmaceuticals to different health centers.

The pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors are commercial enterprises. Their core business is buying and selling pharmaceuticals without any value added to the product. The first change in SCOR is the suppression of ‘Make’ and its plan related process sP3. SCOR defines Make as ‘The process of adding value to products through mixing, separating, forming, machining, and chemical processes’. As a general guideline: These processes are recognized by the fact that 1 or more item numbers go in and 1 or more different item numbers come out of this process (Supply Chain Council, 2006).

⁵ Direct sales to pharmacies mainly concern medicines usually delivered as part of pharmaceuticals advisory and self-medication.

All the level 2 processes and its explanations are presented in the following table:

Process	Characteristics
sP1	“plan supply chain”. sP1 is the development and establishment of courses of action over specified time periods that represent a projected appropriation of supply chain resources to meet supply chain requirements for the longest time fence constraints of supply resources. This is ensured at two levels: the management Control department level who collect, synthetize all information relating to the company on the basis of data processed in different departments (finance, Accounting, cars fleet, order preparation, expedition). This allows the company management “ the second level” to make the right decisions at the right time.
sP2	“plan Source”. sP2 is the development and establishment of courses of action over specified time periods that represent a projected appropriation of material resources to meet supply chain requirements (following the general policy of the enterprise defined in sP1). It’s the planning of the two processes sS1 and sS2. Within the enterprise, the purchasing department guarantee this mission (determination of needs, the purchase orders, storage and also ensure avoiding stock-outs)
sP4	“plan deliver”. sP4 is the development and establishment of courses of action over specified time periods that represent a projected appropriation of delivery resources to meet delivery requirements. It’s the planning of the two process sD1 and sD2. this is done by the coordination of “ “ Customer order preparation service” and “ cars fleet department”. Schedule and frequencies of deliveries are organized according to a delivery plan which consolidates pharmacies according to “ delivery zones “ (distance from the enterprise). The same plan by the customer service.
sP5	“plan return”. A tactical process guaranteed by the “ purchase department” who directs two services: “ Customer return service” who is in charge of monitoring customers returns (sDR1/sDR3), and “ supplier return service” who is in charge of suppliers returns control and monitoring (sSR1/sSR3).
sS1	“Source Stocked product”: the main activity of pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors. sS1 is the process of ordering, receiving and transferring products based on aggregated demand requirements. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Given the particularity of pharmaceuticals sector and its regulation, the wholesale-distributors must take charge of the storage of a significant quantity of medicines that must be constituted of at least 80% of the medicines approved in Morocco. This situation forces them to operate with almost all the laboratories in Morocco (non-existence of suppliers’ selection). - The majority of laboratories are centralised and located in the region of Casablanca. - Two Quality check-up: a pre-control within the laboratory, and a post-control at the arrival of products to the enterprise. - Procurements transport is either carried out by the enterprise transportation (the case of nearby suppliers) or by transport companies (the case of distant suppliers).
sS2	“Source to order product” represents only a small part of the activity. It’s the case of expensive and special non-available products. Also in the case of response to a call tender.
sD1	“Deliver source to stock product” the process of delivering products that were sourced based on the aggregated customer orders (based on sS1) to the community pharmacies. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deliveries are based on the sP4. - The schedule and frequencies of deliveries depend on the “distribution zones”: zone is geographic area consisting of pharmacies. The frequencies of deliveries are determined according to the distance between these zones and the enterprise. (up to 5 deliveries per day for the nearest zones, and a supply per day for the distant zones. - The transport to the nearest zones is carried by the enterprise transportation. For the distant zones, there are cases where transport is ensured by some transport companies.
sD2	“Deliver source to order product” The processes of delivering a product that is sourced in

	response to a specific customer order (based on sS2).
sSR1	“Source return defective product” the return and disposition determination of defective and non-conforming products.
sSR3	“Source return excess product”: the return of excess, aging or obsolete products
sDR1	“deliver defective return product” the receipt (products returned by customers) of the defective and non-conforming product.
sDR3	“Deliver return excess product” the receipt (product returned by customers) of excess, aging or obsolete products

Table 2: SCOR level 2 processes of pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors

2.2. SCOR level 3 modelling

The pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors have as main activity the sale of the ‘source stocked product’. They sell products that are supplied on the basis of aggregated demand requirements (Push system) (sS1 → sD1). The supply to meet a customer order is scarce and represents a small part in their sales.

The process sS1 (figure 7: Not included processes are crossed in red) presented below respects all of the activities described in SCOR. The pharmaceutical sector is very specific. It has a strict regulation (manufacturing, pricing) and reserves the import activities only to manufacturers. Wholesale-distributors source and rely heavily on pharmaceuticals manufacturers.

Figure 7: Level 3 Source processes

The sSR1 / sSR3, sDR1 / sDR3 processes (figure 8) within the company conform to those of the SCOR reference model.

The company receives defectives, aging, obsoletes and no conform products from its customers (sDR1/sDR3). Obsolete products are products in the expiration date is less than:

- 3 months for medicines
- 6 months for other pharmaceutical products.

Non-conform and in a good conditions product will be sent to the warehouse. the remaining products and those that are obsolete in the warehouse will be returned to the suppliers. Generally, two types of suppliers to distinguish: Suppliers who accept returned products (establishing of a credit note), and suppliers who don't accept returned products (a compensatory refund is taken based on the sales of the year).

Figure 8: Level 3 Return Process

The Delivery processes: from the four SCOR delivery processes, only two that exist within wholesale-distributors supply chain: sD1 and sD2. The study focused primarily on the sD1 process.

sD1: Given the specificity of medicines distribution, this process has undergone several changes either by adding new process elements, modifying their SCOR reference orders (both highlighted in green) or by deleting process elements (process elements highlighted in red). Figure 9 shows these changes. For example, activity “sD1.3: Reserve the product and determine the delivery date”: the delivery schedules (see Table 2: sP4) are fixed in advance according to the delivery zones.

Figure 9: sD1 Deliver Stocked Product

2.3. Global view of source stocked product supply chain

We present below (figure 10) the SCOR level 3 model of pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors supply chain for source stocked products. The same model type can be set up for the source to order products.

The SCOR level 2 normally provide an overview of the information flows, and material flows along the supply chain while the SCOR level 3 details all the business process involved in the supply chain.

As we can see on the model, all the activities of the supply chain have been mapped and well represented. All the links between wholesale-distributors and both laboratories and community pharmacies are also identified. In addition to the forward flows, all the reverse flows of products (nonconforming, obsolete and defective products) whether from the community pharmacies to the wholesale-distributors or from the wholesale-distributor to the laboratories, are also well represented.

The changes are highlighted in green, and the notation respects that of the SCOR reference model (The process elements numbering remain the same as that of the SCOR reference model: this explain the order of the process element sD1.6 that is between sD1.11 and sD1.12).

Figure 10: Adapted SCOR level 3 for 'Source Stocked product.'

V. Conclusion and future works

This article focused on the planning and modelling of pharmaceuticals Wholesale-distributors supply chain using SCOR model. It's a first step towards setting up a dynamic and efficient decision-making system in supply chain management of pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors and that consider the uncertainties.

The main objectives of this paper are: (i) to highlight the importance of the wholesale-distributors in the pharmaceutical value chain and the different constraints and difficulties they face and (ii) to present a business process for an adapted SCOR model which can help these enterprises (and other commercial enterprises with the same supply chain characteristics in Morocco and in other developed countries to map, assess and improve their supply chains.

As we discussed in the literature review, the SCOR model is a quasi-standard in supply chain management. Since its development in 1996, several researchers and practitioners worked on its adaptation to different business contexts and environments. It also has had 13 revisions by the supply chain council.

Given the commercial activity of the pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors, the first changes in the modelling of the SCOR level 1 were the suppressions of the "Make" process. For the level 2, we identified 12 processes (from 30 processes proposed by SCOR including Enable processes) and to which we have presented its characteristics.

We focused on the analysis of the "source stocked products" as it's the main activity of the pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors. The process sDI has undergone several changes. A global view of the SCOR level 3 was also presented at the end of the article.

Future works will focus on adapting and enriching SCOR performance indicators to suit pharmaceuticals distribution, then the finalization of the decision-making system of pharmaceuticals wholesale-distributors. In addition, a statistical study to validate our system will be conducted among the 58 Moroccan wholesale-distributors.

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